

Investigation of 30% rule for the combination of component response with the unidirectional principal and critical response spectrum

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Abstract

The ground motion caused by an earthquake can be considered as the resultant of three orthogonal translation components along three Cartesian coordinates x , y , and z ; and three rotational components about these three co-ordinate axes. Though it is well recognized that the response of important structures like nuclear reactor components, dams, tall buildings and long-span bridges, may be dependent on all the three translational components of motion, due to complexity of the three dimensional analysis and various uncertainty in spatial combination procedures, most of the studies in the past considered only one component of earthquake motion. Many investigators have recognized the necessity of finding the response of structures under multi-component earthquake excitation. The vertical component of the ground motion is excluded, assuming that the horizontal components are the governing components for building analysis. In the present study, the validity of the [Max +30%] rule of combining bi-directional response is investigated by comparing the results with the exact results based on the response spectrum in the principal direction [SAXP] and, the critical response spectrum [SACRIT] providing an upper bound to the multi-directional component response.

A typical six storey steel building is modeled as a shear building with lateral and torsional degrees-of-freedom at each floor. Dynamic analysis of the building is performed using CSI SAP2000. Three different sets of real earthquake ground motions, with widely differing characteristics used in the study are Uttarkashi (1991) earthquake, Sikkim (2011) earthquake and Nepal (2015) earthquake. After analysis, it has been found that the [Max + 30%] rule of combining bi-directional response, which is included in IS 1893 (2016) may not lead to realistic results in all the cases. [Max+30%] rule may not work equally well in all cases and it may lead to higher or lower estimates of response when compared with the desired estimate in the principal directional response spectrum. However, in no case, the 30% combination rule exceeds the estimate based on critical response spectrum [SACRIT]. It may be found that estimation of the response of the multi-directional excitation can be performed in a much simpler and efficient way, using unidirectional principal response spectrum analysis. Thus, it can be stated that the Ground Motion Prediction Equations (GMPE) must be developed for the principal as well as the critical response spectrum.

Keywords: Response Spectrum analysis; Principal directional response spectrum; IS 1893 (2016); CSI SAP2000.

1 Introduction

The ground motion caused by an earthquake can be considered as the resultant of three orthogonal translation components along three Cartesian coordinates x , y , and z ; and three rotational components about these three co-ordinate axes.

Many investigators have recognized the necessity of finding the response of structures under multi-component earthquake excitation. Bolotin [1] presented a stochastic theory of structural response to multi-component seismic loading. Penzien and Watabe [2] pointed out the

importance of finding the response caused by three translational components of earthquake motion and studied the characteristics of three-dimensional ground motion.

Chen [3] investigated the statistical dependence of the three components of ground motion. Gelman worked on the combination of the translational component sine of the horizontal direction. Rosenblueth and Contreras [4] developed an approximate procedure for combining the response component. They expressed the resultant response as a linear combination of the components of interest and found the coefficient of expansion so that the

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error is minimized. Wilson and Button [5] presented a method for three-dimensional dynamic analysis for multi-component earthquake spectra.

Other works suggest the methods of combining the maxima of the three components of the response, where each of the component's maxima is found by the customary modal superposition methods using response spectra of the corresponding ground acceleration component. Chu, Amin, and Singh [6] suggested the square root of the sum of the squares (SRSS) method for finding the resultant of three partial responses. The USNRC [7] recommended this method for combining three special responses. The [Max+30%] method suggested by Resenblueth and Contreras [4] is recommended by ATC-3(1978) provisions. In this method; the resultant is taken as the maximum component under consideration plus 30% of the sum of all other components.

Anagnostopoulos [8] made a comparative study of different modal and spatial combination method. In addition to SRSS and [Max+30%] rule, he compared the methods, viz SUM, SRLS and their averages with SRSS. He also used the [Max+40%] and [Max+50%] components, whereas in NRLS method resultant is defined as the maximum of three component plus the SRSS of the other two. This was suggested as a modal superposition method by O'Hara and Cunfit [9].

Though it is well recognized that the response of important structures like nuclear reactor components, dams, and long-span bridges, may be dependent on all the three translational components of motion, due to complexity of the three dimensional analysis and various uncertainty in spatial combination procedures, most of the studies considered only one component of earthquake motion. Hadjian [10] showed that the common spatial combination rules like SRSS and [Max+30%] have been derived on the assumption of statistical independence between components of the response, though such assumption may not be always justified. Anagnostopoulos [8] showed that because of the correlation between components of earthquake motion, additive response effects are created in corner members of the three-dimensional structure. Moreover, all the above-mentioned spatial combination rules combine the maxima of the component's responses to get the maximum of the resultant, whereas the component maxima do not occur at the same time.

Haluk et al [11], considered spectrum intensity concept to investigate the bi-directional effects of earthquakes and the effectiveness of spectrum intensity method. In the study vertical component of the ground motion was excluded, assuming that the horizontal components are

the governing components for building analysis. However, the vertical component can be included in a similar way, when the principal component is in the vertical direction.

In the present work, the authors have investigated the validity of the [Max+30%] rule by comparing the results for a typical 6 storey steel building shown in Figure 1, with the exact results based on the response spectrum in the principal direction and the critical response spectrum, providing an upper bound to multi-directional component response using three different real earthquakes with widely differing characteristics. It has been found that the [Max+30%] rule may not always lead to realistic results.

2 Particulars of the building

A typical six-storey steel moment resisting frame building is considered with 4 bays in the x -direction and 3 bays in the y -direction, as shown in Figure 1. The building is analysed for dead load and appropriate imposed load as specified in IS 1893(2016), considering 5% damping ratio. The time periods (s) for the steel building for the first 9 modes of vibrations and modal participation are given in Table 1.

Figure 1. Typical 6 Storey Steel Building

Table 1. Modal Result

Mode No.	Mode Description	Time Period [Sec]	Natural frequency [rad/sec]	Modal Participation [%]	Cumulative Participation [%]
1	Translation in Y	1.319	4.762	80.54	80.54
2	Translation in X	1.247	5.039	81.79	81.79
3	Torsion in XY Plane	1.215	5.173	-	-
4	Translation in Y	0.409	15.363	10.83	91.37
5	Translation in X	0.405	15.510	10.31	92.10
6	Torsion in XY Plane	0.378	16.613	-	-
7	Translation in Y	0.246	25.505	4.47	95.84
8	Translation in X	0.218	28.786	3.54	95.64
9	Torsion in XY Plane	0.216	29.103	-	-

The visual representation of the first three modes of vibration for the steel building is given in Figure 2.

(2a) Mode-1 (Time Period 1.3195 s)

(2b) Mode-2 (Time Period 1.2476 s)

(2c) Mode-3 (Time Period 1.21457 s)

Figure 2. First 3 modes of vibration of a Steel Building

3 Input Excitation

To perform the numerical study, response spectra of the three real earthquake records are used. The details of the considered earthquakes are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Details of the selected earthquakes

EQ#	Name of EQ	Date	M	Focal Depth [km]	Epicentre distance [km]	PGA [g]	Recording station
1	Gorkha Nepal	25/04/2015	7.9	13.4	13.6	0.754	Kirtipur
2	Sikkim	18/09/2011	6.7	10.00	50.3	0.569	Gangtok
3	Uttarkashi	20/10/1991	6.9	13.2	73.9	1.083	Bhatwari

To compute the response by commonly used [Max+30%] rule, the geometric mean of the response spectra [SAGM] in two horizontal components has been used. To compare these results, it is proposed to use two different spectra; spectrum in the major principal direction [SAXP] and the critical spectrum [SACRIT].

SACRIT is obtained by the resultant response of an SDOF system at each natural period of vibration. Details for computation of SAXP and SACRIT are given below.

3.1 Response Spectrum in Major Principal Direction [SAXP]

Figure 3. Principal directional acceleration ground motion

The response spectrum in the major principal direction [SAXP] is obtained by resolving the components of the original accelerogram record in the major principal direction. Equation (1) Gives the symmetric correlation coefficient matrix used to determine the direction of major and minor principal ground motion,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{yx} & \sigma_{yy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{xx} is the normalised correlation coefficient of the acceleration ground motion in the x-direction, σ_{yy} is the normalised correlation coefficient of the acceleration ground motion in the y-direction and σ_{xy} is normalised cross-correlation coefficient of the acceleration ground motion. These correlation coefficients are obtained as per equation (2), (3) and (4) respectively.

$$\sigma_{xx} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T a_x(t)^2 dt \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T a_y(t)^2 dt \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{yx} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T a_x(t) a_y(t) dt \quad (4)$$

It is known that the cross-correlation coefficients for major and minor principal directions are always zero. Therefore, symmetric correlation coefficient matrix as given in equation (1) is diagonalized by solving the eigenvalue problem for the eigenvalues (λ_1 and λ_2) and corresponding eigenvectors $\{\phi\}_1$ and $\{\phi\}_2$ give the direction of the major and minor principal acceleration ground motion.

Corresponding to the eigenvectors of this transformed new diagonalized matrix gives the directions of major principal ground motion (θ_1) and minor principle (θ_2). Directions for major principal and minor principal ground motion are computed from the equation (5).

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\phi_{(2,1)}}{\phi_{(1,1)}} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\phi_{(2,2)}}{\phi_{(1,2)}} \right) \quad (5)$$

The ground motion in the major principal direction (θ_1) is computed from equation (6).

$$a_{p1}(t) = a_x(t) \cos(\theta_1) + a_y(t) \sin(\theta_1) \quad (6)$$

The response spectrum of an SDOF system for the ground motion as specified in equation (6) is termed as the response spectrum in major principal direction.

3.2 Critical Response Spectrum [SACRIT]

Critical Response Spectrum is obtained by the resultant response $R(t)$ of an SDOF system obtained from SRSS of the response in the x-direction $R_x(t)$ and response in the y-direction $R_y(t)$ for each natural period (T) and damping ratio (ξ). The resultant response of the SDOF system is computed by equation (7)

$$SA_{crit(T,\xi)} = R(t)_{max} \quad (7)$$

where,

$$R(t) = \sqrt{R_x(t)^2 + R_y(t)^2} \quad (8)$$

The computed spectra for the three selected earthquake records are shown in Figure 4. Table 3 gives the spectral amplitudes at the fundamental frequency of the steel moment resisting frame building in x and y-direction.

(4a) Response spectrum of Nepal Earthquake

(4b) Response spectrum of Sikkim Earthquake

(4c) Response spectrum of Uttarkashi Earthquake
Figure 4. Earthquake Response Spectra

Table 3. Spectral Amplitudes at Fundamental Period of Building in x and y-direction

REC #	SAGM [m/s ²]		SAXP [m/s ²]		SACRIT [m/s ²]	
	x	y	x	y	x	y
1	1.17	1.15	1.58	1.53	1.60	1.56
2	0.27	0.24	0.35	0.31	0.35	0.31
3	2.31	2.03	3.68	3.27	3.74	3.36

4 Numerical Analysis and Results

SAGM has been used to compute the maximum displacement and storey shear in both x and y directions of the building using CQC modal combination rules and the resultant response is obtained as follows

$$x_R = x_{max} + 0.3 y_{max} \tag{9}$$

In Equation (9), x_{max} and y_{max} are the maximum responses in x and y directions and x_R is the resultant response in x-direction.

The SAXP spectrum is proposed to get a realistic estimate of resultant response in x or y-direction, simply by unidirectional analysis. Use of SACRIT is proposed to get upper bound in resultant response in x or y-direction. Dynamic analysis is performed with the help of CSI SAP2000 V20.

3D shear steel building model with 2 translational degrees of freedom and 1 torsional rotational degrees of freedom is modeled as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. 3D Model of a typical building in SAP2000

The resultant displacement response of the steel building in x-direction computed using Equation (9) is presented in Figure 6, which compares the resultant response based on the conventional 30% rule with the resultant response

based on only unidirectional analysis using the principal and critical response spectra.

(6a) Storey Displacement for Nepal RS

(6b) Storey Displacement for Sikkim RS

(6c) Storey Displacement for Uttarkashi RS

Figure 6. Storey Displacement

Similarly, storey shear is calculated. The storey shear distribution plot is presented in Figure 7.

(7a) Base Shear for Nepal RS

(7b) Base Shear for Sikkim RS

(7c) Base Shear for Uttarkashi RS

Figure 7. Base Shear Distribution

For Nepal earthquake and Sikkim earthquake, the results obtained by [Max+30%] rule are in a very good agreement with the unidirectional analysis by major principal directional response spectrum and critical response spectrum. But, It is seen that for Uttarkashi Earthquake spectra the response

obtained by [Max+30%] rule is much lesser than that obtained in principal direction response spectrum and Critical response spectra. Thus 30% rule may not be adequate in all cases. As expected; results obtained for critical response spectra are even higher than the principal direction spectrum thus, it can be stated that in no case response due to critical response spectrum can be exceeded. Hence this provides the upper bound to the maximum estimate of the response for a given structure.

5 Conclusions

For Uttarkashi earthquake, depending upon the characteristics of earthquake ground motion results obtained from [Max+30%] rule, the estimate of response are less than the expected results obtained in major principal direction. Hence [Max+30%] rule may not work equally well in all cases and it may lead to higher or lower estimates compared with the desired estimate in the principal direction. However, in no case, the 30% combination rule exceeds the estimate based on critical response spectrum. The following conclusions are drawn based on the numerical investigation.

- a) Estimation of the response of the multidirectional excitation can be performed in a much simpler and efficient way, using unidirectional principal response spectrum analysis.
- b) Ground Motion Prediction Equations (GMPE) must be developed for the principal as well as the critical response spectrum.

6 References

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